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Indentation response of topological lattice

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#ICCM22

Topological Metamaterials

Topological Insulator

Magnetic

Photonic

Mechanical

Acoustic

Kagome

Graphene

SSH

Disordered

Origami

Different Hardness

$P \rightarrow$ Topological Polarization Direction

Indentation Response

Slope \rightarrow Indentation Hardness

Conclusion

- 2D topological honeycomb structure and 3D topological lattice
- Realize different hardness on opposite surfaces: Up to 7 times
- Design guide to achieve a more significant difference of hardness
 - longer edge length
 - the same thickness of ribs and edges
 - smaller wall thickness
 - higher topological degree
 - smaller indenter
- General design rules at the level of both basic unit piece and lattice structure